

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles.—Part IV. The Inadequacy of Werner's Theory to explain Certain Anomalous Cases.

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The action of chloroplatinic acid on various real and potential mercaptans and on some organic sulphides and disulphides has already been studied (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 872; *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1283; *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 133). Recently (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178) a series of complex bodies derived from chloroplatinic acid and ethyl sulphide under different experimental conditions have been described. The compounds may be tabulated as follows :

- (a) Et_2S , PtCl .
- (b) $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2$, PtCl_2 —Six isomers of this composition have been isolated.
- (c) $2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, PtCl_3 .
- (d) $2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, PtEl_4 .
- (e) $2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, PtEl_5 , H_2O .

Some of these compounds have already been discovered by other workers (Blomstrand, *J. pr., Chem.*, 1888, [ii], 38, 852; Tschugaeff and Malschewsky, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 135, 385; Loir, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1853, 39 (iii),

441 *etc.*). The action of organic bases on these bodies, which forms the subject of the present paper, affords some valuable evidence bearing on their constitutions. A part of the work describing the action of ammonia and pyridine on a few of these compounds has been already described (this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 155). In most cases these reactions point unmistakably to the Werner constitution of these complex bodies. In the present paper the work has been extended and the action of primary, secondary and tertiary bases like aniline, benzylamine, ethylamine, piperidine, diethylamine, pyridine, and quinoline has been described.

Action of Bases on PtCl₂, 2Et₂S.

Ammonia, acting on most of the isomerides of the above formula, gives one and the same compound, namely, PtCl₂, 4NH₃. Similarly ethylamine acting on the isomers of m.p.'s 104° and 77° gives PtCl₂, 4C₂H₅NH₂, and benzylamine reacts with the varieties of m.p.'s 96°, 77° and 104° yielding the same compound, PtCl₂, 4C₇H₇NH₂, while quinoline acting on the isomer of m. p. 77° gives PtCl₂, 2C₉H₇N and diethylamine with the compound of m. p. 108° yields PtCl₂, Et₂S, NHEt₂. Pyridine acts on the compound of m. p. 77° giving PtCl₂, 2Py and PtCl₂, 4Py. All these reactions can best be represented on the Werner basis, thus :

where

and

With pyridine, evidently, both the reactions take place, while with diethylamine ethyl sulphide is only partially replaced. All these compounds, however, come under the general category. The compounds with ammonia and pyridine have been already described and that with ammonia has been shown (*loc. cit.*) to have chlorine ions in aqueous solution, as expected from theory.

Action of Bases on PtCl₃, 2Et₂S.

This compound has been found to be split up by crystallisation from alcohol into PtCl₄, 2Et₂S and PtCl₂, 2Et₂S (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178) showing that PtCl₃, 2Et₂S is a molecular compound of the formula [PtCl₃, 2Et₂S], [PtCl₄, 2Et₂S]. This is further confirmed by a study of the action of ammonia, pyridine, aniline, and benzylamine on it. Ammonia has already been shown to give PtCl₂, 4NH₃, which has obviously been derived from the interaction of ammonia with the first component of the molecular compound depicted above. The product of the action of ammonia on the other component has not yet been isolated. Pyridine acting on PtCl₃, 2Et₂S produces [PtCl₃, 2Py], [PtCl₂, 4Py] and another compound which could not be isolated in a state of perfect purity but which appears to be PtCl₄, 2Py. Benzylamine and aniline acting on this compound give PtCl₂, 4C₇H₇NH₂ and PtCl₂, 2PhNH₂ respectively. (The other proposed formula for this compound namely, [Pt(Et₂S)₄]PtCl₆ (*cf. Tschugaeff, Zeit. anorg. Chem.* 1913, 82, 420), though it can give rise to the compound PtCl₃, 2Py, cannot be expected to produce compounds of the type PtCl₂, 4Py and PtCl₄, 2Py, unless the compound first formed, namely, [PtPy₄]PtCl₆ is supposed to break up into

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_4, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

Ammonia and pyridine have already been shown to produce $\text{PtCl}_4, 4\text{NH}_3$ and $\text{PtCl}_4, 2\text{Py}$ respectively by interaction with this compound. These reactions point obviously to the Werner constitution of the body :

But benzylamine and aniline, as shown here, react somewhat abnormally. Benzylamine gives $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$, and aniline two isomers of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{PhNH}_2$, besides aniline hydrochloride. It is quite possible that during the reaction the platinumic platinum is reduced to the platinumous condition as platinumic chloride behaves as an oxidising agent towards organic substances, aniline hydrochloride being formed in the process.

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

While Werner's theory can adequately represent the structures of the compounds $(\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S})$, $(\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S})$ and $\text{PtCl}_4, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, it is not possible to represent the compound $\text{PtCl}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ as a well-defined co-ordination compound. By the action of bases like benzylamine, pyridine, piperidine and ethylamine it gives the following compounds:— $(\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)$, $(\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}, \text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S})$, $(\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})$, $(\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}, \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}, \text{Et}_2\text{S})$, $(\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}, 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N}, \frac{1}{2}\text{Et}_2\text{S})$, $(\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{EtNH}_2)$ and $(\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}, \text{EtNH}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S})$, in all of which the type persists. The production of the above compounds shows that replacement of ethyl sulphide by the molecules of the base occurs but partially. Some intermediate compounds like these are known and have

been studied by Klason and others (*Ber.*, 1875, 28, 1496; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, [2] 67, 53, 39; *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1359 etc.). $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ is thus simultaneously oxidized and reduced—a phenomenon which is rather extraordinary in this series of platinum compounds. As the compound is very soluble in chloroform, its molecular weight was ascertained by the ebullioscopic method and found to be 684, the theoretical value required by $2(\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S})$ being 645. This formula also does not appear to admit of representation according to the co-ordination theory. It is possible, however, to represent it as follows :

which may explain the production of the peculiar compounds (*vide supra*) with two atoms of platinum in one and the same molecule. The actual mechanism of the above reactions is still uncertain and more work must needs be done in this line before its structure can be fully elucidated.

The compound $\text{PtCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, also does not apparently come under the co-ordination theory. Pyridine breaks it up and yields a compound of the formula $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$. But ethylamine gives a compound, $\text{PtCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ in which the PtCl_5 residue remains intact. From this meagre and apparently conflicting evidence it is not possible to assign a constitution to this peculiar compound. Further investigation regarding the action of bases on this compound is, however, in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of $\text{PtCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 77°) with Benzylamine.

The compound, dissolved in a small quantity of the base, was heated on the water-bath for 15 to 30 minutes.

A strong odour of ethyl sulphide was perceptible. On cooling colourless needles separated out which were filtered and washed with a little benzylamine and then thoroughly with alcohol. The substance melts at 196° . It can be recrystallised from chloroform. (Found: Pt=28.63; Cl=10.6; N=8.49. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ requires Pt=28.30; Cl=10.20; N=8.04 per cent.)

Interaction of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 96°) with Benzylamine.

The same compound was obtained as in the previous case. The method was also the same. (Found: Pt=28.5; Cl=10.66 per cent.)

Reaction of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 104°) and Benzylamine.

The same compound was obtained as above. (Found: Pt=27.5 per cent.)

Interaction of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 104°) with Ethylamine.

The platinum compound was treated with alcoholic ethylamine, and the corked flask kept in ice-water for two hours. It was then evaporated spontaneously and the residue dissolved in warm water and concentrated in a desiccator over sulphuric acid. Colourless crystals were obtained, which were filtered and washed with a little water. The substance melts at 142° . (Found: Pt=44.1; Cl=16.5. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{EtNH}_2$ requires Pt=43.9; Cl=15.8. per cent.)

Interaction of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 77°) with Ethylamine.

The procedure was the same as above. The solution after concentration in a vacuum desiccator gave colourless crystals charring at 200° . (Found: Pt=43.7; Cl=15.86. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{EtNH}_2$ requires Pt=43.9; Cl=15.8 per cent.) The mother liquor on complete evaporation left a residue which could be crystallised from a mixture of

alcohol and ether. It has not, however, been sufficiently purified for analysis.

R. action of PtCl₂, 2Et₂S (m.p. 108°) with Diethylamine.

The mixture of the two was heated for five minutes on water-bath when the platinum compound went into solution. On filtering and allowing to stand in a desiccator, yellow crystals were deposited which had the m.p. 176°. (Found: Pt=46.6; Cl=17.2; N=3.55. PtCl₂, Et₂S, NHEt₂ requires Pt=45.7; Cl=16.5; N=3.24 per cent.)

Interaction of PtCl₂, 2Et₂S (m.p. 77°) with Quinoline.

A mixture of the two was heated on the water-bath for about half an hour. The platinum compound dissolved and after cooling it was precipitated with ether. The yellow substance was then re-crystallised from boiling alcohol. It melts at 165°, solidifies on cooling and with further rise in temperature it begins to redden and slightly chars just below 280°. (Found: Pt=38.3; Cl=12.8. PtCl₂, 2C₈H₇N requires Pt=37.5; Cl=13.5 per cent.)

Reaction of PtCl₃, 2Et₂S with Pyridine.

The platinum compound was heated for five hours under reflux with excess of pyridine. The deep orange colour of the substance slowly changed to pale orange. It was then filtered hot, and washed thrice with boiling pyridine. The residue was extracted thrice with boiling water and filtered, and was finally washed with alcohol and dried. It was insoluble in all solvents including chloroform and nitrobenzene. (Found: Pt=42.3; Cl=23.29; N=5.78. PtCl₃, 2Py requires Pt=42.7; Cl=23.09; N=6.07 per cent.) The hot pyridine extract

on standing for 24 hours spontaneously deposited a mass of colourless needles. These were washed with a little pyridine and then with anhydrous alcohol. The compound is highly soluble in water and does not melt or char up to 260°. (Found: Pt=32.4; Cl=11.82; N=10.1. PtCl₃, 4Py requires Pt=33.3; Cl=12.1; N=9.6 per cent.) The aqueous extract on concentration and cooling deposited a yellow compound, which is probably impure PtCl₄, 2Py. (Found: Pt=41.6; Cl=27.7. PtCl₄, 2Py requires Pt=39.6; Cl=28.7 per cent.)

Interaction of PtCl₃, 2Et₂S with Benzylamine.

PtCl₃, 2Et₂S was heated with benzylamine for 1—2 hours. The solution was then treated with alcohol and filtered. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with alcohol. It was crystallised from chloroform and a mixed melting point determination with the compound obtained from PtCl₂, 2Et₂S (m.p. 77°) and benzylamine (*vide supra*) showed no depression. (Found: Pt=28.23; N=8.25. PtCl₂, 4C₇H₇NH₂ requires Pt=28.3; N=8.04 per cent.)

Reaction of PtCl₃, 2Et₂S with Aniline.

The compound was treated with aniline, the mixture shaken up and allowed to stand. The colour of the solution turned orange and then red. On treatment with ether a tarry precipitate came down, which, when boiled with acetone, changed to a yellow granular mass, which was filtered, washed with a little acetone and alcohol and then dried. (Found: Pt=43.88; Cl=16.5. PtCl₂, 2PhNH₂ requires Pt=43.3; Cl=15.6 per cent.)

Interaction of PtCl₄, 2Et₂S with Benzylamine.

The compound was treated with a small quantity of benzylamine, when in a minute or two the colour of the

solution darkened with evolution of heat and the smell of ethyl sulphide was given out. It was heated for half an hour on the water-bath, when colourless crystals appeared, which were filtered and washed first with a little benzylamine and then thoroughly with alcohol. It could be recrystallised from chloroform, and it proved to be identical with $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ described above. (Found: $\text{Pt}=27.8$; $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ requires $\text{Pt}=28.3$ per cent.)

Interaction of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ with Aniline.

The platinum compound was treated with excess of aniline and the mixture heated for half-an-hour on the water bath, when a dark violet viscous solution was obtained. The smell of ethyl sulphide was perceptible. It was cooled and then precipitated by ether. The ethereal extract was kept for subsequent treatment. The pasty mass, thrown down, was filtered and washed repeatedly with ether and then dried and extracted with warm water. The aqueous extract on concentration in a vacuum desiccator gave a small quantity of gray crystals (m. p. 100°) which were filtered and dried (Found: $\text{Pt}=43.4$; $\text{Cl}=14.83$. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PhNH}_2$ requires $\text{Pt}=43.17$; $\text{Cl}=15.00$ per cent.). The mother-liquor on further concentration gave a crystalline precipitate which proved to be pure aniline hydrochloride as shown by analysis and a mixed melting point determination. The residue after washing with water was found to be partially soluble in benzene and acetone, but the substance extracted by these solvents could not be purified sufficiently for analysis. The ethereal extract (*vide supra*) after spontaneous evaporation left a residue, which was washed with a little ether to remove the aniline. The magenta-coloured residue was washed with warm alcohol. The residue became yellow and could be

crystallised from a large volume of acetone. It melts at 190° . and changes to a brown solid, which chars above 205° (Found: Pt = 43.46; Cl = 15.63. PtCl_2 , 2PhNH_2 requires Pt = 43.17; Cl, 15.60 per cent.).

Action of Benzylamine on PtCl_2 , Et_2S .

The platinum compound with benzylamine (in excess) was heated on water-bath for three hours. The colour of the mixture darkened. It was then filtered, and the residue washed twice with hot benzylamine, and then thoroughly with alcohol, when a crystalline white substance was left behind. This was first boiled with alcohol and filtered; the filtrate on concentration and cooling gave a nearly white crystalline compound, which, however, being very small in quantity did not admit of purification and analysis. It melts at 110° , becomes semi-solid and chars above 205° . The residue after extraction with alcohol was repeatedly crystallised from chloroform in colourless needles which were found to be identical with PtCl_2 , $4\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ mentioned above (Found: Pt = 27.5 per cent.). The benzylamine filtrate was treated with ether when a dark brown precipitate came down. It was washed with ether, until it became granular, and was then washed successively with boiling alcohol (the alcoholic extract on standing deposited a yellowish-brown substance, which could not be sufficiently purified), benzene, acetone and finally with chloroform, until the washings were colourless. The residue was soluble in benzylamine from which it could be precipitated by ether. It is a brick-red powder (Found: Pt = 62.00; Cl = 5.34; N = 2.37. The presence of sulphur was proved. Pt_2Cl_2 , $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$, Et_2S requires Pt = 62.8; Cl = 5.6; N = 2.2 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on PtCl, Et₂S.

PtCl, Et₂S and pyridine (excess) were heated on a water-bath for 2-3 hours. The solution was cooled and precipitated with excess of ether and filtered. The precipitate was washed repeatedly with ether and boiling alcohol and then repeatedly extracted with boiling benzene and filtered. The filtrate on cooling gave light yellow crystals, charring above 260°. (Found: Pt=46.8; Cl=16.29. PtCl₂, 2Py, requires Pt=46.24; Cl=16.66 per cent.) The residue after extraction with benzene was boiled with chloroform to remove the unreacted original compound and filtered. The residue was insoluble in all solvents except pyridine, from which it could be precipitated by ether. (Found: Pt=65.2; Cl=6.3, N=2.68; the presence of sulphur was proved. Pt₂Cl, C₅H₅N, Et₂S requires Pt=65.8; Cl=5.9; N=2.34 per cent.)

Action of Piperidine on PtCl, Et₂S.

PtCl, Et₂S with excess of piperidine was heated on a water-bath for 3-4 hours. It was then filtered and washed twice with hot piperidine. The piperidine extract on addition of a large volume of ether and shaking gave a reddish brown granular precipitate, which was extracted repeatedly with boiling alcohol until the filtrate was colourless. It was then washed with boiling acetone, and subsequently dissolved in a minimum quantity of chloroform, filtered, and precipitated with ether. (Found: Pt=60.3; Cl=5.5; N=4.34. The presence of sulphur was proved. Pt₂Cl, 2C₅H₁₁N, $\frac{1}{2}$ Et₂S requires Pt=61.1; Cl=5.0; N=4.03 per cent.)

Action of Ethylamine on PtCl, Et₂S.

The platinum compound with excess of alcoholic ethylamine was kept for four hours in ice water in a

corked flask. The substance went into solution. It was then spontaneously concentrated when a crop of white crystals separated out, which were crystallised from boiling alcohol (Found : Pt=43.5 ; Cl=15.3. $\text{PtCl}_3, 4\text{EtNH}_2$ requires Pt=43.97 ; Cl=85.84 per cent.). The mother-liquor was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator and the residue extracted with warm water. The remaining residue was dissolved in alcohol and evaporated to dryness in a desiccator. The residue was again washed with alcohol when a small quantity of an undissolved compound was left behind. (Found : Pt=69.6 ; Cl=7.00 ; N=2.9. $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_4, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt=69.2 ; Cl=6.3 ; N=2.5 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

$\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added to an excess of pyridine, shaken well and somewhat concentrated by evaporation at the ordinary temperature. Water was added to the mixture and the solution filtered. The residue, a yellow crystalline product, was thoroughly washed with boiling alcohol and benzene. (Found : Pt=40.32 ; Cl=28.18 ; N=5.18. $\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt=39.63 ; Cl=28.57 ; N=5.63 per cent.)

Action of Ethylamine on $\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

To an alcoholic solution of the platinum compound an alcoholic solution of ethylamine was added when an orange precipitate was formed. The alcohol was removed by evaporation at the room temperature, the residue dissolved in water, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. The first crop was obtained as pale yellow crystals in a quantity too small for analysis. The second crop consisted of orange

crystals. These were collected, washed with a small quantity of water and dried in a desiccator. (Found: Pt=42.32; Cl=39.2; N 6.06. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ requires Pt=42.41; Cl=38.22; N=6.03 per cent.)

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